

The minimum distance of particles

Harald Schröder

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We calculate the minimum distance between a positive charged particle Q_2 and an atomic nucleus Q_1 . Q_1 and Q_2 shall be both positive charges and U is the voltage. If a particle has achieved the minimum distance r , the kinetic energy is changed totally in potential energy. If z_1 and z_2 are the particle charge numbers, then we conclude:

$$E_{kin} = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon} \cdot \frac{Q_1 Q_2}{r} = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon} \cdot \frac{z_1 z_2 e^2}{r} \quad (1)$$

ϵ is the electric field constant and e is the electric elementary charge. The relation $E_{kin} = Q_2 U = e z_2 U$ leads to:

$$U = \frac{Q_1}{4\pi\epsilon r} = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon} \cdot \frac{z_1 \cdot e}{r} \quad (2)$$

Equation (1) transformed:

$$r = \frac{z_1 z_2 e^2}{4\pi\epsilon E_{kin}} \quad (3)$$

In the relativistic case it is valid:

$$E_{kin} = mc^2 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}} - 1 \right)$$

m is the mass and v the velocity of particle 2.

We obtain:

$$r = \frac{z_1 z_2 \cdot e^2}{4\pi\epsilon mc^2 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}} - 1 \right)}$$

In the classical case we have $E_{kin} = \frac{mv^2}{2}$. It follows:

$$r = \frac{z_1 z_2 \cdot e^2}{2\pi\epsilon mv^2}$$

Now we will express v in dependence of r . With equation (2) from Schröder [1] it is valid to the relativistic case:

$$v = c \cdot \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{mc^2}{E_{kin} + mc^2} \right)^2}$$

If we express E_{kin} with equation (1) in dependence of r , we get:

$$v = c \cdot \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{4\pi\epsilon r mc^2}{z_1 z_2 e^2 + 4\pi\epsilon r mc^2} \right)^2}$$

In classical case we obtain with $v = \sqrt{\frac{2E_{kin}}{m}}$ and equation (1):

$$v = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2\pi\epsilon} \cdot \frac{z_1 z_2 e^2}{mr}}$$

At last we get from equation (2) to the relativistic case and the classical case:

$$r = \frac{z_1 \cdot e}{4\pi\epsilon U}$$

or as function of energy with equation (1):

$$r = \frac{z_1 z_2 e^2}{4\pi\epsilon E_{kin}}$$

References

- [1] Harald Schröder "Velocity and Temperature" 2009
- [2] Harald Schröder "Particular problems of special relativity theory" Wissenschaft & Technik Verlag Berlin 2002